

TREASURE

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Project no.: **2024-CoARA-022** (CoARA Boost-2024-CALL1)

Acronym: **TREASURE**

Title: **Transforming Research Assessment through
Responsible Research Training of Early Stage Researchers: a
Pilot Study**

Website

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DISCLAIMER:

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1. 2024-CoARA-022-TREASURE Website

1.1 Aims

As part of the Communication and dissemination strategy of the TREASURE project, acknowledged under Project Task 1, a public Website (<https://www.uc.pt/en/iii/treasure/>) was created for transparent and efficient communication of operational details, resources and outputs with all those involved in the program and affected by it (present or future), bridging enrolled members, broader University of Coimbra (UC) community, and external stakeholders.

The public website amplifies the impact and online presence of the TREASURE project, its implementation stories and its results.

1.2 Location, structure and site content

The institutional page was created using the platform UC Pages, the official platform of the University of Coimbra and located within the Institute for Interdisciplinary Research (IIIUC), an interdisciplinary organic unit directed by the Vice-rector for Research, and to which the project was internally assigned. For visual identification, a logo for the project was created (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. TREASURE project's logo.

The page and logo were created and designed by core team members.

The webpage is displayed in both [Portuguese \(PT\)](#) and [English \(EN\)](#) language versions, and it contains information about the Project, its context and funding details (submenu About), People involved (submenu People, displaying Core team, Local and External Advisory Board members), project institutional Location and Contacts (submenu Contacts) (**Figure 2**), highlighting News and Events in the landing page (**Figure 3**). Information displayed in the submenus Local Advisory Board and External Advisory Board ensures accomplishment of Project Milestone 1 – Constitution of Local and External Advisory Boards (**Figure 4**).

Project outputs will be openly accessible in the TREASURE website, in a dedicated submenu (submenu Outputs), with links to related repositories (e.g. Zenodo) when existing.

D.1 Website

The website will be updated throughout project execution according to the defined Tasks and Milestones, to better accommodate the aims and needs of the project and communicate with the UC community.

The screenshot displays the website's navigation and content. The top header includes the University of Coimbra logo, the acronym 'PT EN', and a search bar with 'SIGN IN'. The main navigation menu lists 'About', 'People', and 'Contacts'. The 'Contacts' page is active, showing the address of the Instituto de Investigação Interdisciplinar: Casa Costa Alemão - Pólo II, Rua Dom Francisco de Lemos, 3030-789 COIMBRA | PORTUGAL. An email address 'treasure@[uc].pt' is provided. A map of the location is also shown. Below the contact information are logos for TREASURE, CoARA Boost, and the European Union, along with a disclaimer: 'Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Funded within the framework of the CoARA Boost project under grant agreement No 101131826.'

About

TREASURE: Transforming Research Assessment through Responsible Research Training of Early Stage Researchers: An institutional pilot study

TREASURE is an institutional pilot project aiming to reward master and PhD candidates for implementing reproducible, reusable and open research practices in their thesis research.

We will share more information about opportunities to be involved in developing this new program this spring.

The project is funded under the CoARA Boost cascade grant, a tool from the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) for organisations to implement the 10 commitments aligned in the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) and facilitate institutional change in the context of research assessment.

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Acronym: TREASURE
Title: Transforming Research Assessment through Responsible Research Training of Early Stage Researchers: a Pilot Study
Funding: €30,000

People

Advisory Boards

- EXTERNAL ADVISORY BOARD
- LOCAL ADVISORY BOARD

Core Team

- João Ramalho-Santos: Retoria | IIUC | FCTUC | CNC-UC CIBB
- Tracey Weissgerber: CNC-UC CIBB
- Ana Santos Carvalho: GeneT, CIBB | CNC-UC CIBB
- Bruno Direito: FCTUC | CISUC
- Catarina Domingues: IIUC
- Elsa Henriques: CNC-UC CIBB
- Fernando V. Borges: FDUC | IU
- Inês Almeida: CNC-UC CIBB
- Jorge Noro: IIUC | FEUC | CuBER
- Maria João Neves: NAE | FCTUC | CIAS
- Paulo Oliveira: CNC-UC CIBB

Figure 2. Screenshots of selected contents from TREASURE project’s website, including submenus About, People, and Contacts.

D.1 Website

UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA PT EN

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Q SIGN IN

TREASURE

Treasure

ABOUT PEOPLE CONTACTS

Events

ARCHIVE >

-

20.12.2024
Science Fair CiBB Meeting
-

19.12.2024
Annual Meeting "CERES - 30 years anniversary"
-

12.12.2024
Workshop "Meta-Research in Sport Science"

News

ARCHIVE >

05 November, 2024

Treasure was one of the 25 projects financed in the first round of CoARA Boost

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Figure 3. Screenshot of TREASURE project’s landing webpage.

Funded by the European Union

D.1 Website

👤 / People

Local Advisory Board

The Local Advisory Board holds the core tasks of defining the research practices that will be assessed (adaptable to different research fields); defining assessment criteria and procedures to award the formal recognition (certification), and establishing the qualitative peer review procedures to ensure that criteria were met. It is composed of researchers from different Faculties/Organic Units/R&D Units, at different career stages and holding different roles, including both the assessors and those who will be assessed: Course coordinators, Supervisors, and Early stage researchers (master and PhD candidates).

<p>AT</p> <p>Ana Maria Teixeira FCDEF-UC CIDAF Coordinator of the PhD course in Sport Sciences ORCID</p>	<p>CS</p> <p>Carmen Soares FLUC CECH Coordinator of the PhD course in Food Heritage; Cultures and Identities Co-coordinator of the PhD course in Classical Studies ORCID</p>	<p>CB</p> <p>Carolina Cabeças FMUC CIBT IPM-FMUC CRI ULIS Coimbra PhD student in Health Sciences ORCID</p>
<p>CC</p> <p>Cáudia Cavadas FFUC CNC-UC CIBB Supervisor ORCID</p>	<p>GS</p> <p>Gonçalo Santos FCTUC CIAS Coordinator of the PhD course in Anthropology ORCID</p>	<p>HG</p> <p>Henrique Girão FMUC ICBR-FMUC CIBB Co-coordinator of the PhD course in Health Sciences, Coordinator of the Master course in Biomedical Research ORCID</p>
<p>IF</p> <p>Isabel V. Figueiredo FFUC ICBR-FMUC CIBB Co-coordinator of the Master course in Applied Pharmacology ORCID</p>	<p>JS</p> <p>João Gabriel Silva BIUC CNC-UC CIBB PhD student in Experimental Biology and Biomedicine ORCID</p>	<p>JO</p> <p>João Paulo Faria Oliveira Costa FEUC CeBER Coordinator of the PhD course in Management: Decision Aiding Science ORCID</p>
<p>JP</p> <p>João Peça FCTUC CNC-UC CIBB Coordinator of the Master course in Cellular and Molecular Biology ORCID</p>	<p>JV</p> <p>Jorge Varanda FCTUC CRIA Coordinator of the Master course in Anthropology, Globalization, Climate Change ORCID</p>	<p>LB</p> <p>Liliana Baptista FCDEF-UC CIDAF Supervisor ORCID</p>
<p>LB</p> <p>Lucas Belo FCTUC Master's student in Forensic Anthropology</p>	<p>LD</p> <p>Luis C. Dias FEUC CeBER Supervisor ORCID</p>	<p>LF</p> <p>Luíza Franco FDUC LJ PhD student in Law ORCID</p>

👤 / People

External Advisory Board

The External Advisory Board includes expert members in Research Assessment, Research Integrity, and Responsible Research who developed training tools or implemented related assessment criteria in their institutions.

Its role is to provide additional expertise and insights from other institutions, supporting the Local Advisory Board and the Core Team in the implementation of the program, suggesting strategies, relevant resources, and providing advice on problem solving, while allowing the Local Board to preserve its autonomy and make decisions that will work for the UC community.

<p>BB</p> <p>Bruno Béu FCT Portugal</p> <p>Bruno Béu has a degree and a doctorate in Philosophy from the University of Lisbon, having carried out research and teaching activities in the areas of philosophy of language, literature, aesthetics and linguistics. He joined the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) Evaluation Office as Senior Scientific Officer for the Humanities and Social Sciences area and is currently an advisor to the FCT Board of Directors in the areas of strategy and peer review, having contributed to the design of new FCT programs and their evaluation processes. He is also the director of the new European Research Council (ERC) - Portugal program; the national delegate appointed to the ERC configuration of the Horizon Europe Programme Committee; the national delegate appointed to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Committee for Scientific and Technological Policy; and the national expert appointed to monitor the implementation of European Research Area (ERA) Action 3, dedicated to the reform of the evaluation system. He is Co-Chair of the recently created National Chapter Portugal of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CNP-CoARA), collaborating in the various areas of the research assessment reform process in Portugal.</p>	<p>ML</p> <p>Matthew Luças SSHRC Canada</p> <p>Matthew Luças joined the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC) in September 2015 as the Executive Director, Corporate Strategy and Performance, and has a background in science, technology and innovation policy. Prior to SSHRC, Matthew worked at Industry Canada where he held several positions, including Senior Policy Advisor to the Science, Technology and Innovation Council Secretariat, and the Departmental Advisor to the Minister of State for Science and Technology. Matthew received his PhD from the University of Toronto in 2005.</p>
<p>MK</p> <p>Miriam Kip BHI QUEST Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin Germany</p> <p>Miriam Kip is currently Leader of the Research Group Incentives, and Responsible Research Assessment, at QUEST Center for Responsible Research, Berlin Institute of Health (BHI), Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin. She is also the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) representative from Charité and BHI, and chair of the CoARA working group Supporting the alignment of research assessment systems with CoARA in biomedical disciplines through administrative reforms and governance. Before, she was a Senior Consultant Health Care Research at IGES Institut GmbH. She was a Researcher at the Faculty of Medicine, Otto-von-Guericke University, and resident at Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin. She has a doctoral degree (Dr. med.) in Anesthesiology and is Doctor of Medicine (M.D.) from the Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin. She has also a Master's degree in Global Public Health from the New York University.</p>	<p>NE</p> <p>Natalie Evans Amsterdam UMC The Netherlands</p> <p>Natalie Evans is a Senior Social Scientist and an Assistant Professor in the Department of Ethics, Law and Medical Humanities at the Amsterdam Public Health Institute, Amsterdam UMC. She is a co-founder of the Embassy of Good Science and leads the Research Integrity Programme within her Department. She is an expert in research integrity, research ethics, aging and later life, public health,</p>

Figure 4. Screenshots of submenus Local Advisory Board and External Advisory Board from TREASURE project's webpage, demonstrating accomplishment of Project Milestone 1.